

Cone Beam Computed Tomography In Endodontics (Part III)

Talk

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CBCT and Pre-surgical Assessment

Introduction

Cone beam computed tomography facilitates the clinician to view the relationship of the tooth to its surrounding anatomical structures in a three dimensional view. Cone beam computed tomography with its visual clarity can assist the surgeon in the planning of surgical procedures. The presence/absence of a periapical lesion can change the course of action(s) in any surgical procedures.

The role of cone beam computed tomography in the surgical assessment of maxilla CBCT's guidance enables accurate measurement of the distance between the cortical plate and the palatal root apex. Even the proximity to the maxillary sinus can be evaluated. Using CBCT the size, location and extent of the periapical lesion can be determined. CBCT can meticulously recognise apical pathology as compared to periapical radiology. Clinicians faced difficulty with periapical radiographs, especially in second molar region and areas with close proximity to the maxillary sinus. CBCT could detect the expansion of the lesion into the sinus, missed canals and thickening of the sinus membrane.

The role of CBCT in the surgical assessment of mandible. It is possible to evaluate the dimension of the periapical lesions, the relationship of the mandibular roots to the inferior alveolar canal and buccal bone dimension with CBCT and periapical radiographs before attempting apical surgery. It has been found that a large number of lesions diagnosed with CBCT were undetected on periapical radiography. The dimension of the buccal bone can be ascertained as well thereby stressing on the importance of CBCT assessment in the mandibular quadrant before surgery.

Concluding Remarks

CBCT is recommended for endodontic surgery. CBCT can provide a three-dimensional view of bone topography, tooth anatomy and proximal anatomical structures. CBCT can provide an accurate idea about the quantity and shape of the bone. However, there is less certainty about the quality of the bone. Cone beam computed tomography can be used to visualise the root morphology and thereby influence the outcome of the treatment.

CBCT and Vertical Root Fractures (VRF)

Introduction

Vertical root fractures extend longitudinally from the canal space to the periodontium. They provide a pathway between the oral cavity and the bacteria leading to destruction of the periodontal space and subsequent bone loss. The clinical presentation of vertical root fractures is an isolated periodontal probing depth on either side of the tooth, multiple sinuses and a characteristic 'halo' or 'J-shaped radiolucency. However, these signs may not be associated with long standing or incipient fractures. Vertical root fractures are commonly associated with endodontically treated teeth. Some of common predisposing factors are over zealous root preparation, forces delivered during root canal obturation and intra-radicular post. The prognosis of vertical root fractures is dependent on the location of the fracture and the extent of radicular involvement. Timely and accurate diagnosis can prevent extraction of the concerned tooth. However, these fractures present as a diagnostic dilemma. Clinical features are inconclusive and conventional radiographs are limited in their diagnostic abilities due to compression of a three dimensional anatomy into a two dimensional image, geometric distortion and anatomical noise.

Conventional radiography may not be diagnostically useful in the diagnosis of vertical root fractures unless the x-ray beam coincides with the fracture line. To overcome this hurdle, it is advised that two radiographs be taken with a shift in the horizontal beam. Nevertheless, even after using the parallax method, overlapping may be inevitable preventing the visualisation of the fracture line.

It has been found that the cone beam computed tomography can be promising in the diagnosis of vertical root fractures due to its three dimensional nature, minimal geometric distortion and reduction of anatomical noise.

Concluding Remarks

There is insufficient evidence to advocate the use of CBCT for detection of VRF. However, CBCT may be indicated where symptoms and/or signs are absent or ambiguous and VRF is suspected. In these cases, CBCT may reveal signs of peri-radicular bone loss indicating a VRF within the adjacent root. The artefacts caused in the presence of root filling and intra-radicular

post hinders diagnostic accuracy. The role of CBCT in the diagnosis of VRF needs further clarification and extended research.

CBCT and Resorption

Introduction

Root resorption is defined as the loss of dentin and cementum as a result of osteoclastic activity. The common method of classification is based on the location of the resorption that is external or internal. The process of resorption can continue for up to 2–3 weeks and may present itself as an inconspicuous finding. The process of resorption can be stimulated by pressure or infection triggering osteoclastic resorption of the injured root resulting in extensive damage.

External Cervical Resorption

External cervical resorption (ECR) is mostly initiated by damage to the cementum (usually caused by luxation and avulsion injuries) eventually leading to colonisation of the area by osteoblasts. Furthermore, this condition can be idiopathic in nature. Other causes are trauma, orthodontic treatment and intracoronary bleaching. The diagnosis can be challenging due to the absence of the characteristic 'pink spot'. The radiographic signs are usually an ill defined radiolucency in the cervical third of the root. If the walls of the root canals run through the radiolucent defect, the lesion is external in nature.

Parallax radiography can be used to determine the type of resorption. However, the sensitivity of conventional radiographs is poor in the detection of external root resorption. Furthermore, till the time external root resorption becomes evident on the conventional radiographs, considerable hard tissue damage has already occurred. Also, it is difficult to differentiate between the type of resorption. On the contrary, CBCT can effectively diagnose the type of resorption and the area of extent of the lesion.

Internal Resorption

Internal root resorption is the process of the destruction of the intra-radicular dentin and dentinal tubules. It occurs around the middle and apical region of the canal walls due to osteoclastic activity. A 'ballooning out' appearance is characteristic of internal root resorption. The lesion is oval/round radiolucency with a smooth well defined outline.

Cone beam Computed Tomography or Conventional Radiography?

Resorption may present as a diagnostic dilemma leading to inappropriate treatment. Clinically differentiating between internal and external resorption can be difficult especially without the signs of pink spot, localised gingival inflammation and osseous defects. The first step towards the diagnosis of resorption is conventional radiography. Conventional radiography using the parallax technique can be used to confirm the location (palatal or labial) of the root resorption. The parallax technique does not provide information about the dimension and extent of the lesion. The diagnostic information revealed is incomplete due to the compression of a three dimensional anatomy into a two dimensional shadowgraph. Moreover, anatomical noise results in an underestimation of the size of the resorption.

Various studies have shown that CBCT scans diagnosed root resorption accurately. The software allows selection of a favourable orthogonal view and adjustment of the thickness

between each slice, thus increasing diagnostic susceptibility. CBCT can be a useful in the assessment of root resorption shaping the treatment plan.

It can be concluded that periapical radiograph had a limited accuracy in the detection of the size, circumferential spread and location of external cervical resorptions lesions compared to CBCT.

The additional information gained from CBCT has resulted in the introduction of a 3-dimensional classification to describe external cervical resorption. The aim of this descriptive classification is to ensure an accurate diagnosis and aid communication of external cervical resorption between clinicians. It should allow objective outcome assessment as well as aid in decision making. Ultimately, treatment outcome and prognostic factors may also be assessed in relation to the three dimensional nature of external cervical resorption.

Concluding Remarks

In cases where (parallax) radiographs provide limited information, CBCT should be considered as an additional method to assess the nature of a resorptive lesion; this information improves diagnosis and management of root resorption. CBCT can be a useful tool in the assessment of root resorption thus assisting shaping the treatment plan of a patient as it has higher sensitivity as compared to conventional radiographs. However, most resorptive lesions are unpredictable and occur as incidental findings on routine radiographic assessment. The use of CBCT for routine use is difficult to justify. Limited volume, high resolution CBCT can be used in cases of suspected or established resorption where CBCT can influence the management and prognosis of the tooth.

CBCT and Dento-alveolar Trauma

Introduction

The diagnosis, treatment planning and determination of the prognosis of traumatised teeth is a challenging task. Most commonly used systems for trauma assessment are computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, periapical radiography and cone beam computed tomography. Trauma to the oral region comprises 5% of all dental injuries. The probability of trauma is high in children and adolescents. Incisors are the commonly affected teeth. Effective time management in diagnosis can influence the prognosis of the concerned tooth/teeth. Parallax and occlusal radiographs are recommended for the diagnosis of dental trauma. Even after multiple radiographs taken at several different angles, the fracture line may still not be diagnosed leading to inappropriate treatment and guarded prognosis of the teeth. Commonly misdiagnosed area is the maxillary anterior quadrant due to the oblique nature of the fracture in the sagittal plane.

Horizontal root fractures are classified according to their location and the extent of displacement of the coronal fragment. The prognosis of these fractures is dependent on several factors such as the age of the patient, root development, dislocation and mobility of the coronal fragment. They are common in the maxillary central region (68%), followed by lateral incisors (27%) and rarely mandibular incisors. Root fractures can be horizontal or diagonal in their direction. Detection of these fractures is possible only if the central beam passes through the fracture line. This usually happens with the fractures of the

cervical third.

Cone beam computed tomography can be an asset in the diagnosis and management of dento-alveolar trauma. It has the added advantage of minimisation of anatomical noise and geometric distortion. A single scan can assess the nature and severity of the injuries. Furthermore, the direction of the displacement can be clearly visualised.

Since CBCT is an extra oral technique, it is considered far more comfortable for a patient who has recently sustained dental trauma as compared to several periapical radiographs taken using a paralleling device.

Cone beam computed tomography can effectively detect the nature of the trauma and associated cortical bone defects. Furthermore, CBCT is accurate as compared to multiple periapicals in determination of horizontal root fractures. Rarely single tooth trauma is seen. With the aid of CBCT, multiple teeth are covered in a single scan without the disadvantages of geometric distortion.

Conclusion

It is clear that the additional information provided by CBCT may increase and/or improve diagnostic accuracy and confidence in decision-making as well as have an impact of treatment planning. More clinical studies are required to assess the long-term impact of CBCT on the outcomes of endodontic treatment.

Any effective endodontic treatment is dependent on the accuracy of imaging systems and usually requires radiographic assistance in three stages:

Stage 1- before commencing the treatment to assess tooth morphology and periapical lesion;

Stage 2- working length/master cone radiograph;

Stage 3- that is post-obturation radiograph.

For straightforward endodontic cases, exposure of the patient to CBCT it is not justifiable. CBCT imaging comes at the expense of increased radiation dose; therefore, CBCT should only be reserved for cases where there is potential benefit from a three-dimensional assessment. It is essential that patient radiation exposure is kept as low as reasonably practicable.

The benefits of a CBCT investigation must outweigh any potential risks. Therefore, each scan must be optimized to reduce patient exposure by adjusting the CBCT settings, thus allowing each examination to be personalized to the individual patient and the diagnostic needs, rather than just using manufacturer's default settings.

However, when normal periapical radiography is not in a position to demonstrate accurately the root canal morphology and the clinician is not in a position to formulate his/her treatment plan which would consequentially influence the outcome of the treatment, only then a limited volume, high-resolution CBCT should be attempted.

Prerequisites for CBCT Diagnostics

1. Justification of every radiation exposure after undertaking patient history and clinical examination including periapical radiography. They should add additional information to assist in the patient's management.
2. Risk/benefit assessment should be done for every patient.
3. CBCT should not be used for routine screening of imaging.
4. Radiation dose to the patient should be as low as reasonably practicable.
5. Accurate positioning and patient preparation should be done.
6. Appropriately trained individuals should engage in conducting a scan.
7. All exposures should be reported by a trained individual.

Please note that CBCT must not be used as a substitute to conventional radiography. However, it can be used in some circumstances where clinical and periapical radiographic assessment is inconclusive. CBCT, therefore, offers an advanced direction to improve standards of care. It is safe to state that in the hands of a responsible practitioner CBCT can do wonders to the world of endodontics, expanding diagnostic and treatment possibilities. It is, perhaps, time to welcome CBCT as a part of the endodontic armamentarium, albeit judiciously!

To be continued.....
(It's a review of literature and not an original article)

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